

Globalization: What It Is and What It Is Not?

A Political Economic Perspective of Globalization

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ABSTRACT

Globalization is a term that has entered the political lexicon since the latter half of the twentieth century. Scholars from various disciplines sought to explain and explore the complex and contested nature of globalization, its impacts on the global political economy, and its sustainability. Defined as the growing worldwide interconnectedness, this phenomenon is both commended for fostering economic growth, uplifting millions from extreme poverty, and criticized for exacerbating inequality, cultural imperialism, and new forms of dependency. Perhaps nowhere in the world are these contradictions more evident than in the Global South—a politico-economic division that has undergone profound changes due to globalization, especially since the economic liberalization policies adopted by the respective governments of this region in the 1990s.

Drawing on the perspectives of critical scholars like Marx, Smith, Sameer Amin, Michael Hardt, et.al, this paper critically examines the distributional aspect of globalization. Based on the critical political economic perspective of globalization, it concludes with the argument that globalization may have brought certain opportunities, but its unequal distribution of costs and benefits has reinforced a new form of colonialism, deepened social hierarchies, widened global inequalities, marginalized local economies, and provided MNCs access to a “global labor pool.”

Keywords: Globalization, Income inequality, Global South, New Imperialism, Political Economy of Globalization. Marxist Explanation of Globalization, Critical Introduction of Globalization.

Introduction

Globalization is the term that has entered the political lexicon since the latter half of the twentieth century. Scholars from various disciplines sought to explain and explore the contested and complex nature of globalization, its impacts on the global political economy, and its sustainability. Hyperglobalists argue that globalization is a transplanetary process ushered in unprecedented flows of global trade, finance, and Foreign Direct Investment. It has contributed to successfully elevating many people out of extreme poverty. Their opponents, on the contrary, mostly scholars from the Marxist and critical schools, view globalization as a new form of imperialism characterized by neo-liberal capitalism. Neo-liberal globalization, according to them, has resulted in uneven distribution of wealth and widened the existing income inequality between the Rich North and the Poor South.

The purpose of this article is to provide a critical understanding of neoliberal Globalization, focusing on the distributional aspect of costs and benefits emanating from globalization. It delves into socio-economic and distributional aspects of globalization. It concludes with the arguments that neither the concept nor the consequences of economic globalization are equal for the developed and developing world, owing to divergent socio-economic, political, cultural, and historical legacies that are unique in the context of the Global South.

Globalization: What It Is and What It Is Not

Globalization- the ever-growing interconnectedness or the market expansion in the Marxist lexicon- is the dominant force in our time. Perhaps no other phenomenon has resulted in a heated debate as globalization due to its complex nature, multiple interpretations, and implications. Two seminal books “The Great Convergence” by Richard Baldwin and “Empire” by Michael Hardt and Antonio Negri, offer a stark and diametrical viewpoint of Globalization discourse.

Richard Baldwin offered a new perspective on the study of globalization. In his book “The Great Convergence: Information Technology and the New Globalization”, he argued that the development of information and communication technology has reduced the three historical cascading constraints; “trade costs (cost of moving goods), communication costs (costs of moving ideas, knowledge), and face-to-face cost (cost of moving people)” (Baldwin 2016)¹. Baldwin is of the view that since 1990 the expansion of communication technology accelerated business firms and manufacturing companies of the G7 countries to offshore their labor-intensive and sunset industries to labor surplus regions; from headquarters to factory economy (Baldwin 2016)². The idea of offshore industrialization was guided by a significant wage gap between the Global North and the Global South.

Such deindustrialization of H.Q economies and industrialization of factory economies through the transfer of ideas, goods, technologies, and knowledge will eventually accelerate the economic growth of the emerging economies and they will be able to catch up with the advanced countries. This is what he called the “Great Convergence” which will lead to a more prosperous and just world (Baldwin 2016)³.

The Great Convergence depicts a more optimistic and rosy picture of globalization. It argues that free trade, economic liberalization, and growing interconnectedness create a more prosperous and equitable world in which factory economies will be able to catch up with headquarters. Moreover, offshoring and technology transfer generate economic productivity and uphold their economic condition.

¹ Baldwin, Richard E. *The Great Convergence: Information Technology and the New Globalization*, 2016.
<https://www.amazon.com/Great-Convergence-Information-Technology-Globalization/dp/067466048X>.

² Baldwin, Richard E. *The Great Convergence: Information Technology and the New Globalization*, 2016.
<https://www.amazon.com/Great-Convergence-Information-Technology-Globalization/dp/067466048X>.³
Baldwin, Richard E. *The Great Convergence: Information Technology and the New Globalization*, 2016.
<https://www.amazon.com/Great-Convergence-Information-Technology-Globalization/dp/067466048X>.

Michael Hardt and Antonio Negri, in contrast, offered a more pessimistic view of globalization that is dominated by “Empire”. Unlike traditional empire (lower case), it is a decentralized and deterritorialized form of Empire that operates through the market, global financial organizations, communication technology, and biopolitics (Hardt 2001)³. Hardt and Negri provide an effective tool to analyze the nature of international financial institutions such as the IMF, the World Bank, and WTO. It was seen that these financial institutions used the international debt crisis suffering from many of the third-world countries as leverage to impose their neoliberal policies and sucked the blood of millions of people across the world. Structural Adjustment policies in particular in Latin America displaced millions of people, undermined their livelihood, and threw them under the poverty line overnight. One of the finest examples I would like to cite is from “Poverty, Inc.”⁴ - A documentary directed by Gary Null- in which he showed how NAFTA forced hundreds and millions of people in Mexico to leave farming. Free trade created only less than eighty thousand employment opportunities at the expense of millions of unemployed.

In terms of technological know-how under globalization, capitalism reduced agricultural production into market for MNCs like Monsanto through patents and ‘Intellectual property rights (IPR)’; providing those corporations legal rights to launch their crusade. Such an exploitative economy related to globalization and free trade only results in an exclusive monopoly for corporations and extreme poverty for third-world people.

As Vandana Shiva remarked, “Free trade is free for the giant corporations but means slavery for the peasants in [India] and every part of the world (EURACTIVE 2012).⁵”

Hardt and Toni Negri are right when they termed globalization as an ‘Empire’. This is such an Empire that relies essentially not on the boots on the ground but on transnational networks of markets, corporations, and organizations.

Globalization: A New Form of Imperialism

When Marx said that “Capitalism is inherently global”, he was right. From 1846, he was aware of the fact that “the capitalist economy forms itself as a global system through the formation and expansion of the global market” (Tairako 2003)⁶. This perspective was further elaborated in “Das Capital” that “...with the concentration of capital, there would be a network of market and ultimately, the cosmopolitan nature of capitalist regimes develops (Tairako 2003)⁷.” Although

³ Hardt, Michael, and Antonio Negri. *Empire*. Harvard University Press, 2001.

⁴ Mauren, Kris, James F. Fitzgerald, Jonathan Witt, Magatte Wade, George B. N. Ayittey, Marcella Escobari, Herman ChineryHesse, et al. 2014. *Poverty, Inc.* Edited by Simon Scionka and Tom Small. Directed by Michael Matheson Miller. Widescreen. [Grand Rapids, Michigan]: PovertyCure.

⁵ <https://www.euractiv.com/section/trade-society/interview/full-interview-with-vandana-shiva-on-the-ills-of-the-world-tradingsystem/>

⁶ Tairako, Tomonaga. “Marx on Capitalist Globalization.” *Hitotsubashi Journal of Social Studies* 35, no. 1 (July 1, 2003): 11–16. <https://doi.org/10.15057/8286>.

⁷ Tairako, Tomonaga. “Marx on Capitalist Globalization.” *Hitotsubashi Journal of Social Studies* 35, no. 1 (July 1, 2003): 11–16. <https://doi.org/10.15057/8286>.

globalization was still in the egg during his time, he tried to understand the complex nature of capitalist globalization, reflecting the inherently exploitative nature of global capitalism.

Ronald H. Chilcote defined Globalization as a “politically motivated concept of ideological rhetoric” aimed at reducing conflicts and tensions that disrupt the international political economy (Chilcote 2002)⁸. Throughout his article “Globalization or Imperialism” he argued how the contemporary form of globalization reinforced a new form of Imperialism (Chilcote 2002)⁹.

That’s why, J. Neeraj defined globalization as the “recolonization” in a new grab (Jain 2001)¹¹. Initially, it was envisaged that globalization would bring harmony and equality to the global economy. It was believed the technological transfer from the advanced capitalist world to the Global South would help them to catch up with the global industrialization race. But scholars including Ronald Chilcote, Samir Amin, James Petras, and others who belong to Marxist and critical schools argued that it is nothing but “ideological” discourse that can be best understood as the new clout of imperialism and the imposition of devastating capitalist order (Chilcote 2002)¹⁰. James Petras holds the view that “Globalization serves as an ideological rationalization to “hide class inequality and obscure present world reality (Chilcote 2002)¹¹.” As per Samir Amin, “Contemporary globalization is an ideological discourse that has been crafted to legitimize the strategic interests of the imperialist capitalism; the expansion of capitalism to increase inequalities” (Chilcote 2002)¹².

This idea of globalization contains a particular political ideology and values, meaning that those who embrace and align with the neo-liberal ideology and values eventually become globalized. But the question is, what about those who turn their back on such values and ideology? Cuba, North Korea, and Venezuela can be a good case. Despite living in an unprecedented globalized world, they are not globalized at all. So, according to my perspective, Globalization can be defined as the highest form of capitalist imperialism that flourishes, survives, and sustains in the guise of capitalist ideology and values.

⁸ Chilcote, Ronald H. “Globalization or Imperialism?” *Latin American Perspectives* 29, no. 6 (November 1, 2002): 80–84. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0094582x0202900607>.

⁹ Chilcote, Ronald H. “Globalization or Imperialism?” *Latin American Perspectives* 29, no. 6 (November 1, 2002): 80–84. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0094582x0202900607>. ¹¹ Jain, Neeraj. *Globalisation Or Recolonisation?*, 2001.

¹⁰ Chilcote, Ronald H. “Globalization or Imperialism?” *Latin American Perspectives* 29, no. 6 (November 1, 2002): 80–84. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0094582x0202900607>.

¹¹ Chilcote, Ronald H. “Globalization or Imperialism?” *Latin American Perspectives* 29, no. 6 (November 1, 2002): 80–84. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0094582x0202900607>.

¹² Chilcote, Ronald H. “Globalization or Imperialism?” *Latin American Perspectives* 29, no. 6 (November 1, 2002): 80–84. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0094582x0202900607>.

Globalization and Global Labor Arbitrage

John Smith in his influential work “Imperialism in the Twenty-First Century” argued that one of the fundamental features of neo-liberal globalization is the “global labor arbitrage” or what IMF called the “global labor pool”. It can be defined as an effective tool that helps MNCs to get access to a global pool of labor by offshore outsourcing their labor-intensive or sunset industries to lowwaged emerging economies like India, Vietnam, or Bangladesh (Smith 2015)¹³. It provides twofold benefits to global corporations: firstly, it gives them access to the “global reserve army of labor” and secondly and most importantly, cuts the cost of labor and boosts profits by replacing high-wage workers of the domestic economy with low-wage cheaper foreign workers either through “emigration of production (outsourcing/offshoring industrialization)” or “immigration of workers” (Smith 2015)¹⁴. But irony is companies can freely move, goods and services enjoy free passes but the workers cannot-“a borderless world for everything and everyone except for working-class people” (Smith 2015)¹⁵.

The concept of the Global Value Chain (GVC) which has been advanced with the emergence of globalization and offshore industrialization contributed to facilitating labor exploitation in the lowwage emerging market economies. Bellamy Foster is of the view that outsourcing the production facilities or services in the labor surplus region can drastically reduce the labor cost for the companies. In “The New Imperialism of Globalized Monopoly-Finance Capital,” he argued that even in the contemporary period, the labor cost in the developed world is much higher than in India or China. In India, the labor cost constitutes less than one third of similar labor in an advanced industrialized country (Foster 2015)¹⁶. According to Zahid Hussain, a senior World Bank economist, in the global Ready Made Garments (RMG) industry, which is exclusively located in the Global South, the total labor cost for every garment product is one to three percent of the retail price sold in the global market (Foster 2015)¹⁷. Study shows that in 2010, H&M, one of the top

¹³ Smith, John. “Imperialism in the Twenty-First Century.” *Monthly Review* 67, no. 3 (July 2, 2015): 82. https://doi.org/10.14452/mr-067-03-2015-07_6.

¹⁴ Smith, John. “Imperialism in the Twenty-First Century.” *Monthly Review* 67, no. 3 (July 2, 2015): 82. https://doi.org/10.14452/mr-067-03-2015-07_6.

¹⁵ Smith, John. “Imperialism in the Twenty-First Century.” *Monthly Review* 67, no. 3 (July 2, 2015): 82. https://doi.org/10.14452/mr-067-03-2015-07_6.

¹⁶ Foster, John Bellamy. “The New Imperialism of Globalized Monopoly-Finance Capital: An Introduction.” *Monthly Review* 67, no. 3 (July 1, 2015): 1. https://doi.org/10.14452/mr-067-03-2015-07_1.

¹⁷ Foster, John Bellamy. “The New Imperialism of Globalized Monopoly-Finance Capital: An Introduction.” *Monthly Review* 67, no. 3 (July 1, 2015): 1. https://doi.org/10.14452/mr-067-03-2015-07_1.

fast fashion companies in the world, was paying its workers only 2-5 cents per shirt produced by their arms-length of Bangladesh (Foster 2015)¹⁸.

Historical imperialism and the presence of “global reserve army of labor” are one of the reasons behind low-wages, keeping labor costs in the periphery below the average value of labor power (Foster 2015)¹⁹.

Such extreme forms of exploitation in the apparel sectors of Bangladesh, the manufacturing industries of China, or other labor-intensive industries that are being experienced by the millions of low-wage workers in developing countries are the result of neoliberal globalization (Smith 2015)²⁰. So, Smith is of the view that “neo-liberal globalization must be recognized as a new imperialist stage of capitalist development, where imperialism is defined by its economic essence that is the exploitation of southern living labor by the northern capitalists” (Smith 2015)²¹.

Globalization and Female Labor Force

Another important development of neo-liberal globalization is the feminization of the labor force and labor flexibility. It simply denotes the sharp increase of women from the agricultural sector to the industrial sector and the flexibility of women’s labor (Saidul 2016)²². According to the authors, offshoring industrialization in low-income countries provided ample opportunities for women who needed money and corporations motivated by low-cost, high profits (Saidul 2016)²³. Over the years, the participation of women in global manufacturing industries is overwhelmingly increasing characterized by the feminization of labor. For example, according to the 2022 labor force survey, women constitute around 55.57 percent of the total RMG workforce (Express 2024)²⁶.

¹⁸ Foster, John Bellamy. “The New Imperialism of Globalized Monopoly-Finance Capital: An Introduction.” *Monthly Review* 67, no. 3 (July 1, 2015): 1. https://doi.org/10.14452/mr-067-03-2015-07_1.

¹⁹ Foster, John Bellamy. “The New Imperialism of Globalized Monopoly-Finance Capital: An Introduction.” *Monthly Review* 67, no. 3 (July 1, 2015): 1. https://doi.org/10.14452/mr-067-03-2015-07_1.

²⁰ Smith, John. “Imperialism in the Twenty-First Century.” *Monthly Review* 67, no. 3 (July 2, 2015): 82. https://doi.org/10.14452/mr-067-03-2015-07_6.

²¹ Smith, John. “Imperialism in the Twenty-First Century.” *Monthly Review* 67, no. 3 (July 2, 2015): 82. https://doi.org/10.14452/mr-067-03-2015-07_6.

²² Islam, S., Hossain, I. (2015). Globalization, Gender and Labor Rights: Trends and Trajectories. In: Social Justice in the Globalization of Production. International Political Economy Series. Palgrave Macmillan, London. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137434012_3

²³ Islam, S., Hossain, I. (2015). Globalization, Gender and Labor Rights: Trends and Trajectories. In: Social Justice in the Globalization of Production. International Political Economy Series. Palgrave Macmillan, London. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137434012_3 ²⁶ The Financial Express. “Women Account for 55pc of Garment Workers.” The Financial Express, n.d. <https://today.thefinancialexpress.com.bd/trade-market/women-account-for-55pc-of-garment-workers-1719244417>.

In explaining the reason behind this trend, Elson and Pearson argued that “female labor must either be cheaper to employ than their male counterpart or have higher productivity or some combination of both, resulting that the unit cost of production is lower with female labor” (Saidul 2016)²⁴. Feminization and labor flexibility serve as a process that on the one hand provides temporary employment for women without any labor rights or benefits on the other hand, it offers greater leverage to the corporations “to hire and fire” and women workers are kind of best suit for this process (Saidul 2016)²⁵.

Globalization and Income Inequality

The debate over globalization and the distribution of wealth can be explained from two ideological standpoints; hyper globalist and radicals. According to liberals and hyper globalist, economic globalization contributed to reducing global poverty and inequality (Kacowicz 2013)²⁶. As World Bank Report says, the percentage of world population living in extreme poverty has decreased from 36percent in 1990 to about 10 percent in 2015 (World Bank 2018)²⁷.

The volume of global trade and finance have grown 6.2 trillion USD in 2000 to nearly 30.4 trillion USD in 2023 (WTO 2024)²⁸ and in terms of FDI, 1.3 trillion USD in 2023 (UNCTAD 2024)²⁹, compared to 788 billion USD in 2000.

Accordingly they argue that economic globalization has substantially increased international trade, facilitated cross border investment and contributed to reducing extreme poverty globally.

Radicals, conversely, critique hyperglobalists and argue that a strong nexus between globalization and income inequality is evident. It has led to deepening and widening the existing gap between the rich and the poor within and between countries (Kacowicz 2013)³⁰. Melinda Mills and other scholars also maintained that although economic globalization has reduced extreme poverty in some extent, it is increasingly linked with inequality and the socio-economic gap between haves

²⁴ Islam, S., Hossain, I. (2015). Globalization, Gender and Labor Rights: Trends and Trajectories. In: Social Justice in the Globalization of Production. International Political Economy Series. Palgrave Macmillan, London.

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²⁵ Islam, S., Hossain, I. (2015). Globalization, Gender and Labor Rights: Trends and Trajectories. In: Social Justice in the Globalization of Production. International Political Economy Series. Palgrave Macmillan, London.

https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137434012_3

²⁶ Kacowicz, Arie M. *Globalization and the Distribution of Wealth*, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9781139227117>.

²⁷ World Bank Group. “Decline of Global Extreme Poverty Continues but Has Slowed: World Bank.” *World Bank*, September 19, 2018. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2018/09/19/decline-of-global-extreme-poverty-continuesbut-has-slowed-world-bank>

²⁸ Secretariat, Wto. “WTO Blog | Data Blog - Thirty Years of Trade Growth and Poverty Reduction.” WTO Blog, n.d. https://www.wto.org/english/blogs_e/data_blog_e/blog_dta_24apr24_e.htm.

²⁹ UNCTAD. “World Investment Report 2024,” June 20, 2024. <https://unctad.org/publication/world-investment-report-2024>

³⁰ Kacowicz, Arie M. *Globalization and the Distribution of Wealth*, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9781139227117>.

and have-nots. This social inequality exists not only in the Global South but also within the social hierarchy of the Global North. Mills, in her article- Globalization and Inequality- maintained that even though globalization increased both relative and absolute income of individuals, there are definitely winners and losers within the system (Mills 2009)³¹. Drawing empirical evidence she showed that a particular section of society, like corporate CEOs, higher officials, owner of the tech giants, are the most secured groups from the force of globalization (Mills 2009)³². In other words, some well positioned individuals, entrepreneurs and states become wealthier while the rest are either left out of the race or become exposed to the force of economic globalization (Kacowicz 2013)³³. Unlike India or China, for example, Nepal and most of the African and Sub-Saharan states do not have capacity or technological prowess to get benefit from the globalization. They do not have much to offer instead of undermining their traditional economic system connecting with volatile global market. The net worth of Elon Musk – owner of the Tesla- will definitely be higher than the combined GDP of many African states.

IMF in its 2018 seminal work, acknowledged that the gains from globalization is not equally distributed within countries. It is seen that in many countries, most of the national income is ended up into the pocket of handful people while leaving no significant effect on the poor (Tavares 2018)³⁴. The world inequality report highlights the extent of global income and wealth inequalities. According to the WEF Global Inequality Report, at the global level when it comes to wealth, the poorest half of the population owns just 2% of the global total, while the richest 10% populations own 76% of total global wealth (World Economic Forum 2024)³⁵. In the South Asian context, this number is quite high. As for the case of Bangladesh, around 44 percent of the total national income is held by 10 percent of the population,³⁶ whereas in the neighboring country India, “the richest 1 percent people now own more than 40 percent of the country’s total wealth and the rest of the population together share just 3 percent of wealth,” cited by the Hindu.³⁷ IMF suggests that economic globalization is one of the driving forces behind excessive social inequalities across the world. According to the report, the uneven distribution of income not only causes income divergence across the world but also within the country. Such discrepancies may exist in the form of offering disproportionate benefits to the affluent class of society (Tavares 2018).

³¹ Mills, M. “Globalization and Inequality.” *European Sociological Review* 25, no. 1 (July 18, 2008): 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcn046>.

³² Mills, M. “Globalization and Inequality.” *European Sociological Review* 25, no. 1 (July 18, 2008): 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcn046>.

³³ Kacowicz, Arie M. *Globalization and the Distribution of Wealth*, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9781139227117>.

³⁴ Lang, Valentin, and Marina Mendes Tavares. “The Distribution of Gains from Globalization.” *IMF Working Paper* 18, no. 54 (January 1, 2018): 1. <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781484347065.001>.

³⁵ World Economic Forum. “These Charts Show the Growing Gap between the World’s Richest and Poorest,” September 10, 2024. <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2021/12/global-income-inequality-gap-report-rich-poor/>.

³⁶ <https://www.thedailystar.net/news/bangladesh/news/inequality-increasing-2913046>

³⁷ <https://frontline.thehindu.com/news/oxfam-inequality-report-2023-says-indias-richest-1-per-cent-own-more-than-40-per-cent-of-total-wealth/article66382782.ece>

Conclusion

Based on the above discussion, it can be said that the contemporary form of globalization is a “fragmented globalization”. The costs and benefits emanating from neo-liberal globalization is contradictory for both developed and developing world owing to socio-economic, political, cultural and historical trajectories which is unique in the context of the Global South. However, in order to reduce the negative externalities of neo-liberal globalization, Amartya Sen is more interested on sociological approach based on satisfying factors not only income but also the social and cultural domains (Mills 2009)³⁸. He argued that we need to go beyond econometric analysis to examine inequality in personal freedoms. Whether everyone is equally enjoying the health, education, and their basic needs (Mills 2009).³⁹ This approach highlight the distributional justice of globalization. Other scholars like Kacowicz and Paul focused on the reinvigoration of the domestic capacity of national governments (Paul 2021)⁴⁰ and a strong state-society relationship (Kacowicz 2013).⁴¹ If it happens, we can envisage a global economy that is “embedded in society” and will ensure an equitable distribution of resources (PAUL 2021).⁴²

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³⁸ Mills, M. “Globalization and Inequality.” *European Sociological Review* 25, no. 1 (July 18, 2008): 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcn046>.

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⁴¹ Kacowicz, Arie M. *Globalization and the Distribution of Wealth*, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9781139227117>.

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